

SIMULATION OF SUPERSONIC FLOW CHARACTERISTICS IN A GROOVED DIVERGENT ROCKET NOZZLE USING COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS

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Abstract

The convergent-divergent design of the nozzle of a rocket engine is the most defining part of it. The nature of the nozzle design enables it to convert the high pressure, temperature and relatively low velocity adiabatic expanding gaseous fluids into very high velocity and thrust gases. The rapidly exiting gas as a consequence of the rapid expansion process results in low pressure and temperature. It is critical in research to find out the influence of modification (grooves) would have in the application and design of a reaction device such as a rocket engine. The Computational Fluid Dynamics software, Analysis System (ANSYS) was employed together with necessary boundary conditions to design and simulate such a modified rocket engine nozzle. The interaction and relationship existing among the pressure, velocity, Mach number and temperature in the grooved divergent rocket nozzle was found and observed. From the plots and nozzle simulation contours, both velocity and Mach number increased rapidly along the nozzle area but decreased steadily. Pressure varied directly with temperature and inversely with density. It is observed that divergent nozzle grooving influences the velocity, Mach number, pressure and temperature within the divergent nozzle area of a rocket nozzle.

Keywords: Compressible Flow; Velocity; Mach number; Divergent Grooving; Navier-Stokes equations

1.0 Introduction

Rocket Propulsion Technology is a critical field of study where rocket engines are designed to convert very high-pressure, high-temperature fluid flow from combustion in the combustion chamber into high-velocity exhaust jet of gas to high thrust in an attempt to move or propel the vehicle forward. Typical or traditional rocket engines or motors comprise a convergent-divergent (CD) geometry nozzle called a "De Laval" nozzle. The converging section accelerates the flow to speeds equal to the speed of sound (sonic conditions) at the throat, and then the divergent nozzle section which is the expansion region/zone further accelerates the flow to speeds higher than the speed of sound called supersonic velocities. Though the fundamental engineering principles of converging-diverging nozzles are well-established, researchers are still engaged in redesigning and engineering advanced nozzle concepts capable of giving improved performance, efficiency and capabilities such as enhanced flow control, altitude adaptation and thrust vectoring. One of these modified concepts is the grooved divergent rocket nozzle, where axial grooves are incorporated into the walls of the divergent nozzle area.

Grooving in the expanding section of the nozzle area may significantly alter the dynamics of flow in a channel compared to a plane surface devoid of grooving. Secondary flow patterns, delay of flow separation and induced boundary layer changes can result in altering the propulsive and aerodynamic performance of a jet or rocket engine. Comprehending, critically modelling and designing the flow dynamics is very important for optimizing the performance of a grooved divergent rocket engine. Smith et al. (2002) mentioned that many numerical, analytical and computational approaches have been studied, explored and used to model the dynamics of fluid flow in grooved pipes, conduits and its flow on or around structures and bodies. The use of Computational Fluid Dynamics modelling and simulation of flow physics problems offers a highly comprehensive way to depict or represent such flows as boundary layer effects, shock waves, turbulence and many more (Jones et al., (2005); Kim et al., (2007)).

Computational Fluid Dynamics therefore makes it quite convenient and cost-effective while saving a lot of time when trying to understand or solve a particular physics flow problem.

The application of Computational Fluid Dynamics concerning flow around or through grooved bodies needs careful thought when it comes to the modelling of turbulence, numerical schemes and grid generation to ensure some level of accurate predictions. Park et al. (2015) and Lee et al. (2016) mentioned in their studies that, by exploring the various design parameters that accompany structures incorporated with grooves such as their depth, width, inclination and spacing, their performance and efficiency of either a rocket nozzle or any device having grooves, can be maximized. According to Howard (2012), Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is a field of study that utilizes computers to predict solutions to problems relating to fluid dynamics based on appropriate governing equations of fluid motion. Zhang et al. (2021) asserted that CFD plays an integral role in fluid mechanics studies as well as other complex fields of studies such as aerospace, meteorology, shipbuilding, petrochemicals and many more that will however be quite impossible to solve with the use of CFD. Grooving has found wide usage when it comes to its effects and myriad applications in various fields of physical studies. Many researchers have experimented and at the same time researched the effects of having grooves on or within structures. Mohd et al. (2022) in their paper on internal grooving using a magnetic field system, mentioned that researchers were engaged constantly in an attempt to improve fluid flow efficiency, heat transfer, and fluid flow velocity amongst other fluid flow characteristics. According to Shamooun (2021), improving the efficiency or performance of fluid flow could be affected by making appropriate alterations, such as the number and dimension of modules. Srivastav (2012) studied Flow Control over Airfoils using different shaped dimples. It was observed that a flight lift structure had a reduced drag coefficient when compared with a classical airfoil without modification. Watt and Fish (2001) examined the performance of an airfoil with varying bumps on the leading edge of whale flippers. They found out that, a modified wing designed to have the latter modifications experienced about 4.8 % increment in lift, 10.9 % induced drag reduction and about 17.6 % lift-to-drag reduction. Zonouz and Salmanpour (2012) studied the flow field and transfer of heat through a

2D wavy duct using numerical analysis. They observed that by simply making the wavy grooves sharper, the transfer of heat increases considerably axially along the length of the conduit.

The Navier–Stokes equations of fluid flow forms the fundamental law utilized by CFD to solve fluid flow problems and they can be subsequently modified to suit certain fluid flow criteria by removing terms describing viscosity, diffusion, external and internal forces to yield the Euler equations.

1.1 Fundamental design principles of rocket nozzle design

The convergent-divergent nozzle design of a rocket engine plays a critical and integral role in reaction engine propulsion system development. The nozzle is responsible for converting the high temperature, high pressure of a compressible fluid into high velocity and thrust jet exhaust necessary for propulsion. Well-established in literature are the principles of compressible flow dynamics forming one of the critical aspects upon which the design principles of rocket science are based. The "De Laval" nozzle is made up of the converging and diverging section that accelerates the flow of the fluid to sonic conditions which occur at the nozzle throat section, followed by the diverging section that expands and accelerates the fluid flow further to higher speeds greater than the speed of sound. The optimal expansion ratio which is the ratio of the nozzle exit area to throat area ratio forms one of the critical principles of the design looked at to obtain optimal operating conditions, such as the pressures in the chamber. The optimal expansion ratio also helps determine the degree of the expansion of the flow (Sutton and Bilbarz, (2010), Huzel et al. (1992).

There are other design principles which can influence significantly, the performance of a rocket engine and one of these is the nozzle Contour design. Commonly used nozzle contours include the parabolic, bell and conical nozzles. Each of these latter nozzle shapes or designs comes with its distinct benefits and trade-offs pertaining to weight, ease of manufacture and efficiency (Bao and Zheng, (2011); Rao, (1958)). The effects of the boundary layer also play a critical role in the design consideration of a rocket engine as the effects of viscous flow near the walls of the

chamber can lead to the separation of flow and its subsequent degradation. Boundary layer control and cooling which are control techniques have been researched by researchers to curtail these effects (Mach and Schramm, (2021); Arrington et al.,1996).

1.2 Isentropic fluid flow relations and compressible theory of flow

A special case of adiabatic fluid flow where the entropy of a fluid system remains the same and constant throughout the process is the isentropic flow (Cengel and Cimbala, (2018)). For a compressible and one-dimensional flow, these below relations hold:

$$M = \frac{v}{a} \quad (1)$$

Where M, the Mach number, is the ratio of the fluid local velocity, v and the local speed of sound, a.

Eq. (2) is the relation linking the stagnation (total) pressure, P_o , to the static pressure P. The stagnation pressure is the pressure of a fluid when it is brought to rest without any decrease or loss in mechanical energy.

$$\frac{P_o}{P} = \left(1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} M^2\right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}} \quad (2)$$

γ stands for the adiabatic constant or specific heat ratio of the fluid.

The stagnation (total) temperature, T_o , is related to the static temperature, T, through the relation:

$$\frac{T_o}{T} = \left(1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} M^2\right) \quad (3)$$

Compressible fluid systems are one of the areas that utilize the isentropic flow relations in their design and analysis.

Turbomachinery, nozzles and diffusers are also among some of the devices (Munson et al, (2013)).

1.3 Nozzle geometry and performance

The fundamental conceptual design and construction of the rocket engine nozzle deeply relies on the design geometry which has huge effects on the general working and performance of the convergent-divergent engine

leading to the conduction of many research studies in the attempt to investigate and understand the efficiency and overall performance of rocket engines.

Higher nozzle chamber pressures alongside improved specific impulses are achieved by redesigning better cooling design systems and nozzle materials. Nozzle cooling is very important in determining rocket engine performance since it increases engine operational or working time by improving the resistance to excessively high temperatures. Ablative and regeneratively cooled nozzles due to their mode of operation are capable of withstanding higher temperature nozzle operations as compared to their uncooled counterparts which results in much higher working chamber pressures and other performance parameters.

In a nutshell, certain design parameters such as the expansion ratio, nozzle contouring, cooling design and nozzle geometry play a very important and critical role in determining the performance criteria of a rocket nozzle and critical design considerations thus employed can result in better engine performance and thrust production.

1.4 Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) modelling

A powerful tool that is used for the analysis, prediction and solution of complex flow phenomena in a broad range of applications is the Computational Fluid Dynamics tool. Numerical simulations of flow problems are conducted using various computational models or methods together with some algorithms. Anderson (1995) mentioned that CFD modelling has influenced and is used in various fields including the automotive industry, turbo-machinery, environmental engineering and the aerospace engineering industries among others. It was further asserted that CFD had become a significant tool employed in the design, optimization, analysis and prediction of performance when it comes to complex flow phenomena of fluids.

The Navier-Stokes equations form the fundamental basis describing various phenomena related to how fluid flows and its interaction with solid bodies or the physical environment. These fundamental equations comprise a set of equations namely: the conservation of mass also known as the continuity equation, momentum and energy equation.

The equation of state is also employed in the solution of flow problems - it relates pressure, temperature and volume in a thermodynamic equilibrium. By discretizing the partial differential equations present in the flow equations using various techniques from numerical analysis to transform them into sets of algebraic equations and solving them computationally, a solution is hence obtained.

The level of accuracy of computational predictions of flow problems offered by Computational Fluid Dynamics tools makes it a great niche to explore and develop further. It offers significant influence in many fields of study especially in the engineering, mathematical, physics and chemical science fields. The ability to select the best modelling technique further validates the significant impact it has in the prediction of complex flow problems and phenomena (Wilcox, (2006)).

The evolution of flow studies will continue to rely on the development and utilization of high-end numerical simulation techniques in the analysis and improving the performance of flow through rocket nozzles. More comprehension of complex flow problems within rocket nozzles would lead to the advancement of more efficient and reliable nozzles or other systems designed by scientists when CFD, experimental and moderately reduced-order models are fused in their employ for flow problem prediction.

1.5 Computational Fluid Dynamics of grooved body configuration

The use of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) has become an invaluable tool in the analysis and optimization of nozzle designs, particularly when investigating the complex flow patterns and heat transfer phenomena associated with grooved body configurations. Huzel and Huang (1992) mentioned the importance of including CFD modelling in the design process of rocket engines. They stressed the importance of appropriately and accurately modelling the heat transfer and fluid dynamics to obtain reliable rocket engine performance and prediction.

1.6 Novel groove geometries and their impact on nozzle performance

Quiet recent innovations in rocket nozzle design are the design of variable rocket engine nozzles by altering and studying the effects of nozzle geometry shapes fundamentally. The exploration and investigation of novel nozzle geometries by incorporation of patterns, changing angles of convergence and divergence are among the various ways of modifying rocket nozzles to obtain certain outcomes or behaviours in flow separation, boundary layer effects, heat transfer rates and general nozzle performances.

In a relatively recent study, it was mentioned that by amalgamating certain variations in rocket nozzles, certain benefits in performance output could be obtained by analytically placing, positioning and re-modifying rocket engine nozzles which can aid in reducing the effects of flow separation in over-expanded nozzles. When the flow characteristics and boundary layer are changed, modified nozzles can lead to performance improvement, efficiency and even introduce flow stability (Sutton and Biblarz, (2017)). Rao (1958) through analytical means led to the introduction of the "Rao Nozzle" by incorporating contouring into the conical nozzle design to generate the bell nozzle rocket engine. The Rao nozzle offered better performance and efficiency and helped deal with the issue of boundary layer and flow separation better than the conical nozzle. Huzel and Huang (1992) further emphasized the significance of understanding the underlying fluid dynamics and heat transfer phenomena within grooved nozzles, as these factors can have a significant impact on the overall engine performance and reliability. The authors stressed the need for comprehensive computational fluid dynamics (CFD) modelling and experimental validation to optimize the design of these novel nozzle concepts.

As the aerospace industry continues to push the boundaries of rocket propulsion, the exploration of innovative groove geometries and their integration with advanced manufacturing processes is expected to play a crucial role in the development of more efficient, versatile, and high-performing nozzle designs.

1.7 Advanced-Adaptive rocket nozzle concepts

Due to changing mission requirements for rocket engine nozzles, the need for modification or redevelopment of existing available propulsion technology has become very critical and crucial. A niche of growing research interest is the investigation of variable-geometry rocket engine nozzles, which result in the change of shape and size during operation due to changing ambient conditions. The benefits of changing nozzle shape geometry such as improved efficiency and performance lead to optimal operation in virtually all conditions such as pressure, leading to versatility and adaptability (Sutton and Biblarz, (2017)). Stark (1999) mentioned that it was important to augment real-time monitoring and feedback control systems to improve rocket engine performance.

Real-time monitoring and control of the performance of rocket nozzles can also play a critical role in improving nozzle performance by constantly sensing and providing the required feedback to rocket engine components to control their operation in changing conditions

2.0 Methodology

Higher thrust is generated by driving the rapidly expanding and flowing gases to achieve greater velocities. The nature of the rocket nozzle helps determine the flow characteristics of the fluid characteristics.

2.1 Computational procedure

Meshing and boundary conditions

High resolution, structured and a double precision mesh was generated to adequately capture flow over grooved regions along the nozzle wall for its rapid convergence and provision of smooth fluid flows. The resulting mesh obtained is seen in Figure 2. The boundary conditions for the flow inlet, outlet and wall along with the respective pressures as given in Tables 2 and 3 coupled with the required initial conditions.

Figure 1: Grooved Nozzle Design

Figure 2: Grooved Nozzle Mesh

The Ansys Design modeller was utilized in capturing the dimensions captured in Table 1 of both Conventional and Grooved convergent-divergent rocket nozzles as shown in Figures 1 and 2.

The physical coordinates and the generalized coordinates provided by the mapping function:

$$\eta = \eta(x, y) \quad \xi = \xi(x, y)$$

According to the equation above, $x = x(\xi, \eta)$ and $y = y(\xi, \eta)$.

The mesh creation procedure establishes the corresponding functional coordinates, and the governing equations are transformed into corresponding equations that are partial derivatives of the parametric space based on their interaction.

For a flow system with two dimensions,

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial T}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial T}{\partial \eta} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial T}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial T}{\partial \eta} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial y} \quad (5)$$

The two equations for the inverse transformation are as follows:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial \xi} = \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\delta T}{\delta y} \frac{\delta y}{\delta \xi} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial \eta} = \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \eta} + \frac{\delta T}{\delta y} \frac{\delta y}{\delta \eta} \quad (7)$$

Eq. (4) through to (7) are the chain rule transformation from physical (x,y) coordinate frame to a generalized computational coordinate system (ξ, η) which form the fundamentals for the transformation of grids.

The following equations represent the form of the solved Poisson Equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial y^2} = M(\xi, \eta) \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial y^2} = N(\xi, \eta) \quad (9)$$

Grid clustering or spacing is controlled by two functions, M and N. As M and N approach zero, finer grids result.

Table 1. Geometric dimensions of the grooved divergent rocket nozzle.

Nozzle Section	Grooved Nozzle Dimension, mm
Convergent nozzle angle A10	19.385°
Divergent nozzle angle A32	13.282°
Combustion chamber length L2	10.829
Combustion chamber width L3	16.244
Rocket engine length L5	75.000
Divergent nozzle axial length L18	42.554
Nozzle exit radius L16	19.474
Throat radius L7	9.4303
Groove width L19, L26, L27, L29	5.9763
Groove depth	0.5599

2.1.2 Residual plots

These were important in identifying the nature of the computational solution based on iteration. The local imbalances of conserved variables present in each respective control volume are measured by the residuals.

The solver used for this study is Analysis System Fluent and it solves the modified governing flow equations due to wall modification and boundary conditions.

2.1.3 Result generation

Convergence arrives at the end of the iterative solutions, The respective plots and data contours are obtained describing the flow analysis of various flow properties through the Convergent-Divergent rocket nozzle.

2.1.4 Analysis procedure and boundary conditions

Table 2.CFD PreProcessing Setup.

Procedure	Setup
Problem Setup: General-Solver	Type: Density-based
Models	Energy:On
Materials	fluid: Air (25 ⁰ C)
Boundary Conditions	Inlet: Pressure Inlet, Gauge Total Pressure (90 kPa) Outlet: Pressure Outlet Gauge Pressure Static Temperature: 288.1K Wall: Wall function
Reference Values	Compute from: Inlet, Reference Zone: Solid body surface.

Monitors	Create walls, Print to console and plot
Initialization	Standard initialization, Compute from inlet
Solution	Solution controls- Courant number= 5, Run calculation: Enter iteration number and initiate.

Table 3.Material library.

Quantity	Description
Material	Air at 25°C at 1 atm
Option	Pure substance
Thermodynamic State	Gas
Density	1.185 kg m ⁻³
Molar mass	28.96 kgkmol ⁻¹
Specific heat capacity	1.0044E03 Jkg ⁻¹ k ⁻¹
Reference fluid temperature	25°C
Thermal conductivity	2.61E02 Wm ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Thermal Expansivity	3.35E-03 K ⁻¹

2.2 Mathematical formulation

Governing fluid flow equations

Conservation of mass

This is also commonly referred to as the “continuity equation” of flow which states that mass in a system cannot be created nor destroyed but can only move from one place to the other. In partial differential form, it is represented by Eq. (10) in its compressible form.

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho v)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(\rho w)}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (10)$$

u, v and w represent the velocity components in the x, y and z directions.

Conservation of momentum

In the conservation of momentum, the application of the second law of Newton to a control volume is carried out and when forces are applied to control volumes, changes in the momentum are observed. The control volume is influenced by two main forces, the external body forces and the surface which induces pressure and viscous forces into the volume which get incorporated into the momentum equation.

X-component of momentum equation

$$\frac{\partial(\rho u)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u^2)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho uv)}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) + \rho F_x \quad (11)$$

Y-component of momentum equation

$$\frac{\partial(\rho v)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho uv)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho v^2)}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} \right) + \rho F_y \quad (12)$$

Where u and v represent the velocity components in the x and y directions respectively.

F_x , F_y and p are the additional surface forces and pressure respectively. These forces are the normal and shear viscous stresses in two-dimensional xy directions incorporated into the control volume.

Conservation of energy equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left[\rho \left(e + \frac{v^2}{2} \right) \right] + \nabla \cdot \left[\rho \left(e + \frac{v^2}{2} \right) \mathbf{V} \right] = \rho \dot{q} - \frac{\partial (up)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial (vp)}{\partial y} + \rho \mathbf{F} \cdot \mathbf{V} \quad (13)$$

Thermal equation of state where R is the specific gas constant is given in Eq. (14) which links pressure and density.

$$P = \rho RT \quad (14)$$

Thermodynamic relation between the state variables encapsulates the entire equation and for a calorically ideal gas with constant specific heat, e is given in Eq. (16) with Eq. (15) showing e to be a function of T and P.

$$e = e(T, P) \quad (15)$$

$$e = c_v T \quad (16)$$

Boundary conditions

Inlet

$$u = 1, v = 0$$

Outlet

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = 0 \text{ for fully formed flow at the outlet of the grooved convergent-divergent nozzle.}$$

Wall

No slip and isothermal boundary conditions.

From the Continuity equation in divergence form below, a fluid particle moving from left to right under the influence of a pressure gradient within the fluid stream and to satisfy the law of the conservation of mass diverges whenever it impacts a body, reconstitutes behind the body and hence maintaining the total fluid mass at the right side of the fluid path. The above statement is represented by the equation below:

The fluid velocity vector, $\vec{V} = (u, v)$ in Eq. (17) for flow in twodimensions and x and y are the streamwise and normal coordinates respectively.

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{V} = 0 \quad (17)$$

Bounding the fluid flow field equations are two non-permeating and non-slip boundaries/walls identical in shape and area represented by $\vec{V}_{yt} = \vec{V}_{yb}$ where \vec{V}_{yt} is the velocity experienced by the upper wall boundary and \vec{V}_{yb} is the velocity of the lower boundary. Beyond the upper and lower walls or boundaries, it is assumed that flow is zero for normal flow through a duct as given in Eq. (18).

$$Y_{tx} \leq y \leq Y_{bx} \quad (18)$$

Y_{tx} and Y_{bx} stand for the upper and lower wall shape of the convergent divergent nozzle shape.

2.2.1 Periodic conditionality of flow through repeating grooves

Wall condition

With regards to the flow through a hollow duct with periodically repeating structures or grooves, the mathematically repeating or changing cross-sectional area is represented as Eq. (19 and 20) (Patankar et al. (1977)).

$$Y_{tx} = Y_t(x + l) = Y_t(x + 2l) = Y_t(x + 3l) = Y_t(x + 4l) \quad (19)$$

$$Y_{bx} = Y_b(x + l) = Y_b(x + 2l) = Y_b(x + 3l) = Y_b(x + 4l) \quad (20)$$

l , x and $(x + l)$ are the period of change which is a characteristic dimension, horizontal positions present within the grooves.

2.2.2 Evolution of fluid flow cyclic/periodic velocity, pressure and temperature

Let the two-dimensional flow velocity be $u(x, y)$ and $v(x, y)$.

$$u(x, y) = u(x + l, y) = u(x + 2l, y) = u(x + 3l, y) = u(x + 4l, y) \quad (21)$$

$$v(x, y) = v(x + l, y) = v(x + 2l, y) = v(x + 3l, y) = v(x + 4l, y) \quad (22)$$

Eq. (21 and 22) depict the nature of the fluid flow passing through a duct and over periodic structures or grooves.

2.2.3 Modification of periodic pressure flow through a varying nozzle

$$p(x, y) - p(x + l, y) = P(x + l, y) - p(x + 2l, y) = P(x + 2l, y) - p(x + 3l, y) = P(x + 3l, y) - p(x + 4l, y) \quad (23)$$

$$P_a(x, y) = -\beta x + \hat{P}(x, y) \quad (24)$$

From Eq. (24) β , P_a are the linear constant pressure and the actual corrected pressure respectively for a definite mass flow rate. The above equation shows the pressure axial pressure decline along the grooved nozzle with successive groove presence.

The analysis of the Mach number, temperature, pressure and density are obtained from the ratio of the relations below:

The ideal gas speed of sound is provided in Eq. 25 and Eq. (26) gives the Mach number.

$$c = \sqrt{\gamma RT} \quad (25)$$

$$M = \frac{v}{c} \quad (26)$$

Where v and c are the velocity of an object or particle and the speed in its surrounding medium respectively.

The fluid flow temperature is increased when flow is stagnated leading to the converting of kinetic energy into enthalpy.

The equations of flow at stagnations result in some stagnation properties for temperature, pressure and density (T_o, P_o, ρ_o) respectively given in Eq. (27 to 32).

$$c_p = \frac{\gamma R}{\gamma - 1} \text{ and } c^2 = \gamma RT$$

Temperature

$$T_o = T + \frac{v^2}{2c_p} \quad (27)$$

Pressure

$$\frac{p_o}{p} = \left(\frac{T_o}{T}\right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}} \quad (28)$$

Density

$$\frac{\rho_o}{\rho} = \left(\frac{T_o}{T}\right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}} \quad (29)$$

Pressure Variation

$$\frac{p_o}{p} = \left(1 + \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{2}\right)M^2\right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}} \quad (30)$$

Temperature

$$\frac{T_o}{T} = \left(1 + \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{2}\right)M^2\right) \quad (31)$$

Density

$$\frac{\rho_o}{\rho} = \left(1 + \left(\frac{\gamma-1}{2}\right)M^2\right)^{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}} \quad (32)$$

At this point, utilizing the conservation of mass and the isentropic mathematical relations, the Area-Mach number relation is obtained in Eq. (33).

$$\frac{A}{A^*} = \frac{1}{M} \left[\frac{2}{\gamma-1} \left(1 + \frac{\gamma-1}{2} M^2\right) \right]^{\frac{\gamma-1}{2(\gamma-1)}} \quad (33)$$

The nozzle area is given by “A” and the throat area is represented by “A^{*}” making Mach number, M at any point in the convergent-divergent a function of the ratio of the nozzle area and the throat area.

3.0 Results and discussion

Figure 3: Velocity-Temperature plot

Figure 4: Axial Velocity plot

High Kinetic energy gas entities are generated in a rocket nozzle when high-pressure and temperature gases undergo rapid adiabatic expansion. It is assumed that all thermal energy is used to propel the molecular gaseous species. Figure3 describes the effect of streamwise temperature on the velocity of a grooved divergent rocket nozzle. Beyond the nozzle-throat section, the high-temperature gases are converted to high-velocity gases speeding out through the outlet of the rocket nozzle and as such, the higher the thermodynamic conversion, the greater the velocity of the exiting gases. Due to the continual thermodynamic conversion of thermal energy to high-velocity gases, there is always a relatively lower temperature experienced aft the nozzle-throat area as compared to the rest of the grooved nozzle.

Figure 5: Grooved nozzle velocity contours

Figure 6: Grooved nozzle Mach number contours

Along the axial length of the rocket engine, the speed of the fluid changes from being subsonic within the combustion chamber, sonic at the nozzle-throat junction and supersonic while travelling out of the divergent or expansion nozzle section. For a compressible gas such as that employed in the computational analysis above, a decrease in pressure as observed in Figure9 and 13 occurs axially in the rocket nozzle leading to an increase in the velocity of the molecular entities forming the working fluid. The temperature also decreases axially since part of the thermal energy is used to perform work on the molecules propelling them to higher speeds and velocities. From Figures 4 and 5, it is observed that the velocity of the moving gas rapidly increases steeply axially towards the exit nozzle until around the nozzle throat region where the velocity for the grooved divergent nozzle increased further closer to 600 ms^{-1} and steadily decreased to a little over 550 ms^{-1} .

Mach number is a dimensionless quantity and a function of local flow velocity to the speed of sound in a medium and as such the velocity of exhaust gases rushing out the rocket nozzle determines the Mach number. Velocities below the speed of sound are referred to as subsonic with a Mach number less than 1. Mach numbers more than 1 and equal to 1 are termed supersonic and sonic respectively.

Figure 7: Mach number versus velocity.

Figure 8: Axial Mach number Plot

Bernoulli's principle fundamentally explains that as the pressure of a fluid increases, its relative velocity decreases hence creating an inversely proportional relation. The effect of axial distance on the Mach number for a grooved nozzle is given in Figures (6 and 8). Mach number and velocity are directly proportional which is observed from Figures 4 and 5 that, velocity increases axially along the nozzle area and this presupposes that mach number will equally increase axially. From Figure 7, the direct proportional relation between Mach number and axial velocity is shown. Mach number increases from within the combustion chamber to the nozzle throat where Mach number is 1 and from the convergent-divergent junction, the Mach number increases sharply to a maximum supersonic Mach number of about 3 and 2.8. Within the grooved section of the nozzle, regions with unique patterns were Mach numbers ranging between 2.1 to 2.5. This decrease in Mach number can be attributed to the presence of grooves and their subsequent interaction with fast-moving fluid in the divergent nozzle section.

Figure 9: Mach number-pressure plot

Figure 9 shows that, as the pressure within the grooved rocket nozzle increases, the resulting Mach number decreases accordingly and the reverse is equally true whereas pressure decreases axially, the Mach number also increases.

Figure 10: Density versus Temperature plot

Figure 11: Grooved nozzle Density contours

Figure10 shows the relationship existing between the density and temperature of the working fluid within a convergent-divergent rocket nozzle. Figure 11 also shows the contours of density within a grooved divergent rocket nozzle where density is seen to decrease axially towards the nozzle exit area. As the temperature increases, the

density of the fluid decreases making Density to be inversely proportional to temperature. An increase in temperature results in an increase in the kinetic energy of the fluid molecules which in turn energizes fluid species further propelling them wide apart unless the species are confined in a closed system. Both Figure 10 shows density decrease with temperature increase whereas Figure 11 gives the contours of density decline aft the grooved divergent rocket nozzle. Density has a sharp decrease at a temperature range of 120 K to 140 K.

Figure 12: Grooved nozzle pressure plot

Figure 13: Grooved nozzle pressure contours

In the nozzle, isotropic flow is observed making pressure change directly proportional to the temperature. Pressure is observed to be maximum within the combustion chamber and inlet. Pressure is observed to decrease towards the convergent throat area until the nozzle exit area. Figure (12 and 13) show the attitude of pressure within the grooved divergent rocket nozzle. Figure 12 shows that pressure increases as temperature increases and Figure 13 gives the contours of pressure from the combustion chamber streamwise to the grooved divergent exit nozzle area. Figure 13 also shows contours of pressure with a sudden decrease in pressure observed from aft the nozzle throat exit section towards the rear of the throat. A minimum pressure of 2.877×10^3 Pa is observed at the grooved nozzle exits.

Figure 14: Grooved nozzle Total Temperature contours

Figure 14 depicts the total temperature contour distribution and it is seen that the contours of total temperature for the grooved nozzle generally have a temperature reading of between $2.999 \times 10^2 \text{K}$ to $3.004 \times 10^2 \text{K}$ but for the regions around the grooves which have different temperature readings or contours. There are four main temperature stratifications present within the grooved nozzle exit ranging from 2.994×10^2 to 3.004×10^2 with the central nozzle core having a similar temperature as the rest of the rocket nozzle.

4.0 Conclusion

This study discussed the fundamental basics relating to grooving in a convergent-divergent rocket nozzle and provided a computational simulation analysis of the supersonic fluid flow conditions on velocity, Mach number, pressure, density and temperature.

Mach number curve was not smooth due to the presence of perturbations leading to changing pressure change within the grooved divergent sections. Velocity was found to be directly proportional to Mach number but inversely proportional to density and density. The total temperature was also found to be dominant around the nozzle surface with grooves.

Grooved divergent nozzle geometry will have a significant impact on nozzle output performance should more research be channelled towards its study to achieve maximum performance efficiency with grooving in rocket nozzles.

Authorship Contribution Statement

Dieu-Donne TallaElbazarWandaogo: Conceptualization, Methodology, writing-original draft, writing review.

Christian J. Ewtire: Supervision, Investigation and Formal Analysis. Douglas KwasiBoah: Supervision, Resources and Visualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

We the authors declare that no conflict of interest exists in the submission of this manuscript and that the manuscript is approved by all authors for publication. We do not also have any form of commercial associative interests that represent a conflict of interest in connection with the work submitted.

Data Availability Statement

Data are contained within the article

Nomenclature

a	Local speed of sound
M	Mach number
v	Local velocity
P_o	Stagnation (total) pressure
P	Static pressure
γ	Adiabatic constant or specific heat ratio of the fluid
ρ	Density
h	Enthalpy
C_p	Specific Heat Capacity at constant pressure
∇	Divergence of a vector
u, v	Velocity components in x, y and z directions
μ	Dynamics viscosity
$\bar{\rho}$	Mean flow density
\bar{v}	Mean flow velocity
\bar{V}	Velocity Vector
\bar{V}_{yt}	Flow velocity along the upper wall boundary
\bar{V}_{yb}	Flow velocity along the bottom wall boundary
l	Periodic distance length scale
P_c	Constant relating to pressure
L	Length
\hat{P}	Modified pressure

ν kinematic viscosity
 k Thermal conductivity

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